

Popular Article

Biopesticide: An Eco-friendly Approach to the Aquaculture Practice

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Introduction

Biopesticide is one type of eco-friendly pesticide which is mainly derived from natural material such as animals, plants and microbes. Nematodes, plants (e.g. Chrysanthemum, Azadiracthaindica), microbes (e.g. Bacillus thuringiensis, Tricoderma, Nucleopolyhedrosis virus) which are the parental material of biopesticides

Three major classes of biopesticides

- Microbial Biopesticides
- Plant incorporated Biopesticides
- Biochemical Biopesticides

Table 1: summarized 3 types of biopesticides

Microbial biopesticides	Plant incorporated biopesticides	Bio-chemical biopesticides
Products which consist of microorganisms as active ingredients. Mainly utilized fungi, bacteria and virus. Ex. <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Here, genes inserted into the plant tissue and pesticides produce inside its own. Ex. Bt canola, Bt cotton, Bt potato etc.	Naturally occurring substance that control pests by non-toxic mechanisms. Ex. Azadiractin from Neem tree.

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As a biopesticide extraction of Neemazadiractin is one of the most versatile and well known which contains at least 35 biologically active compounds such as antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal and insecticidal properties (Murussiet al., 2015).

Earlier to remove the predatory fish from aquaculture pond different types of synthetic pesticides were used. These pesticides have long term persistency in the water and also contaminate the aquatic environment. Therefore, in the present situation, biopesticides are replaced with those harmful synthetic pesticides (Saravana et al., 2010). Biopesticides are gained much more attention due to its non-persistency and low bioavailability in the environment.

Azadiractin has been successfully used in aquaculture to control the predator fish and different pest (Saravana et al., 2010). Sometimes, it also prevents bacterial and viral infections in aquaculture farms. The dose of these biopesticides is most important because a high dose of biopesticides is slightly toxic towards the non-targeted organisms (Murussi et al., 2015 and Saravana et al., 2010). Magnolia officinalis extract can be used as anti-protozoan activity, which is used to inhibit or causes mortality of *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis* (holotrichous ciliate) that affect the fresh water fish farming.

Significance

- Biopesticide is a systematic pesticide mainly acts upon target organism and closely related organisms (Saravana et al., 2010).
- These are decomposed very quickly and bioavailability is very low.
- It is an integrated approach to ensure ecosystem and conserve biodiversity.
- It is replaced the synthetic pesticides and reduce the contamination in aquaculture farm and enhances the ecosystem-based aquaculture for sustainability (Murussiet al., 2015).
- Biopesticides are also prevented bacterial, fungal and parasitic infections in fish culture (Kumar et al., 2013).
- Inhibit the growth of weeds.
- More effective than chemical pesticides in the long term.

Hindrances

- High levels of these substances are slightly toxic to the non-targeted organisms (Saravana et al., 2010).
- Sometimes the speed of action of these pesticides is very low.

- Biopesticides are highly specific, mainly act upon the targeted species.

Future prospect and Conclusion

Biopesticides are eco-friendly to the environment. In the present situation, acceptances of these substances are increased among the farmer due to its low marketable value and environmental safety. Due to the use of biopesticides revolution occurs in aquaculture practice. In the future, much more research is required to standardize the optimal dose of different biopesticides for non-targeted organisms.

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